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Abstract

A high potential exists for discovering placer minerals on the Alaskan continental shelf. The eastern Bering Sea shelf may have the greatest potential for locating gold placers. The shelf areas offshore of Nome and Goodnews Bay, Alaska, deserve special emphasis in the search for offshore gold placers. East of Cape Prince of Wales and off St. Lawrence Island there is also potential for heavy mineral placers. Offshore Seaward Peninsula appears to have high potential for tin.

The Washington and Oregon Outer Continental Shelf (OCS) offers opportunities for developing placer deposits. A full suite of heavy minerals occurs along these coasts. Occurrences of gold flakes and platinum with other heavy mineral sands have been found along the Washington coast from Cape Flattery to the Columbia River. Offshore Crescent City, California, has potential for offshore platinum and gold.

Kyanite and sillimanite are the dominant heavy minerals on the eastern Gulf of Mexico shelf. The amphibole-pyroxene group are dominant in the western Gulf of Mexico shelf.

Heavy mineral placers are abundant and widespread on the Atlantic OCS. Areas offshore of Florida, South Carolina, and Virginia have potential for containing economically viable heavy mineral placers. Many of the shelf sands are titanium rich. Other minerals included in the suite are rutile, ilmenite, zircon, garnet, kyanite, sillimanite, and staurolite.

Resource estimates for offshore undiscovered placers range from tens of millions of ounces of gold in Alaska to millions of tons of heavy minerals off the Pacific coast. The Atlantic OCS may contain well over a million tons of titanium alone.

I. INTRODUCTION

Placers are mineral deposits formed by the weathering of parent rocks and mechanical concentration by the action of rivers, waves, and currents. Although placer deposits occur in rivers and lakes as well as in offshore marine environments, this discussion focuses primarily on the occurrence of placer deposits on the continental shelves of the United States.

A significant amount of metals are imported into the United States and some placer metals are important to the economy of the United States and critical to the defense industry. Examples of important heavy metals and minerals that can occur as placers include gold, platinum, cassiterite, chromium, ilmenite, rutile, zircon, and monazite.

The availability of several of these metals is dependent upon foreign suppliers. For example, the United States, which does not produce chrome ore, is heavily dependent upon imports from southern Africa. South Africa and the USSR are the two principal producers of platinum accounting for 90 percent of world output. Canada is the only other significant producer of platinum (Murphy, 1980). Ilmenite and rutile ores are a source for titanium, which is commonly supplied to the United States by Australia and Canada. Prices for these metals in the United States can increase from reductions in world supplies, which can in turn direct attention to our continental shelves as sources for placer metals.

BACKGROUND

The occurrence and residence times of placer minerals on the shelf are influenced by the tectonic framework of the coastal region and the geomorphology and environmental setting in which the placers are deposited. In light of recent plate tectonic theory, the east coast of the United States is an example of a trailing edge coast. This type of coast faces a seafloor spreading center situated on stable portions of the plate and is typified by broad continental shelves that slope into deep water without a bordering trench. Coastal plains are wide and low lying with major drainage systems. Placers on the shelf adjacent to a trailing edge coast are likely to have long residence times and contain a mature suite of minerals; except on glaciated shelves where immature suites of minerals are dominant.

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The south coast of Alaska is an example of a collision coast. This type of coast occurs along the leading edge of a continent where two crustal plates collide or come into contact by moving one over the other. The coast is characterized by narrow continental shelves bordered by oceanic trenches and deep basins. The onshore areas are predominantly rugged with mountainous topography and are seismically active. Placers on the shelf adjacent to a collision coast are likely to be numerous and well sorted owing to high energy transportation and concentration processes.

A third type of coast is a marginal coast that tends to develop along the shores of continental sea and is typically bordered by a wide continental shelf and shallow sea with an irregular shoreline. Coastal plains are common and vary in width. Deltas often develop owing to extensive river discharge into the sea in concert with reduced wave action associated with shallow moderately sized water areas. The Gulf of Mexico coast is an example of a marginal coast (Gorsline and Swift, 1977). Placers are also likely to occur on a shelf adjacent to a marginal coast where drainage patterns migrate through mineral bearing country rock.

Alaskan Shelf

The continental shelves adjacent to Alaska include the southeastern Alaska shelf, the Gulf of Alaska, the Bering Sea, the Chukchi Sea, and the Beaufort Sea. Together they cover an area of 2,149,690 km² (830,000 sq mi) about 74 percent of the total 2,900,785 km² (1,120,000 sq mi) of the continental United States shelf (Sharma, 1979). Parts of the Alaskan shelf form a broad transition zone between continental crust and oceanic crust while other parts of the shelf display a distinct boundary.

Pacific Shelf - (Washington, Oregon, and California)

The Pacific shelf area can be subdivided into three regions which reflect differences in wave energy, morphology, and sediment input. A narrow continental borderland exists in southern California north to Point Conception. This continental borderland is characterized by a basin and ridge submarine topography with depths significantly less than those of the deep ocean. Further north, the shelves are narrow or even absent along the mountainous coast from Point Conception to Monterey Bay. Near San Francisco, the shelf again widens and maintains its width off Oregon and Washington and becomes more complex (Shepard, 1973). The topography of the continental shelf off Washington is fairly smooth and deepens gradually seaward to the edge of the continental shelf.

The Pacific coast is influenced by subduction zones to the north and south resulting in mountain building, earthquakes, faulting; all the symptoms of a seismically active region. In several cases, submarine canyons extend beyond river mouths to oceanic depths.

Gulf of Mexico Shelf

The Gulf of Mexico (GOM) continental shelf and slope is a vast region encompassing nearly 697,000 km² (433,000 sq mi) as compared with about 1,862 km² (1,157 sq mi) for the entire western U.S. Atlantic Shelf. Water circulation in the GOM is primarily gyral in nature. From east to west, the Gulf of Mexico shelf can be subdivided into five regions based on major sediment type and morphology: (1) the Florida Limestone Plateau; (2) the Big Bend of Florida-Alabama-Mississippi; (3) the Mississippi Delta Shelf; (4) the West Texas-Northern Mexico Shelf; and (5) the Campeche-Yucatan Limestone Plateau (Gorsline and Swift, 1977).

Atlantic Shelf

The Atlantic shelf varies in width from less than 10 km (6.2 mi) off Miami, Florida, to more than 150 km (93.2 mi) off New York. Considerable differences in climate, meteorological events (e.g., storms), and the physical character of the shelf results in the east coast experiencing a wide range of oceanographic conditions. Several of these include a mean southerly drift over the central and southern Atlantic shelf and lower mean wave height and shorter wave periods relative to the west coast.

Seismic refraction studies have shown a thick sequence of sediments, presumably Mesozoic and Cenozoic Coastal Plain material, off the northwestern coast of the United States (Burk and Drake, 1974). The shelf off the southeastern coast combines areas rich in terrigenous clastics separated by areas lacking detrital material and dominated by biogenic debris (Gorsline and Swift, 1977). The effects of glaciation are apparent throughout New England, the Gulf of Maine, New York, and Long Island. These effects extend to the offshore on the northeastern continental shelf in the form of till-like deposits of gravel, sand, and silt found on parts of the Gulf of Maine and Georges Bank shelf (Ross, 1970).

RESOURCES

Gold and Platinum - Alaska Region:

The continental shelf of the eastern Bering Sea adjacent to northern Alaska may have the highest potential for gold placers anywhere in the United States. Onshore placers to the east have produced nearly a third of the placer gold produced in Alaska. The shelf area offshore of Nome and Goodnews Bay, in particular, deserve special emphasis in the search for offshore gold placers (Tagg, 1979). Submerged shorelines and stream channels may be prime localities for gold placers. One area of high interest begins about 15 km (8 miles) west of Nome and continues to Cape Nome,

about 21 km (11 miles) east of Nome. Other important, but less significant, locations where gold placers may be uncovered include a prominent shoal NNE of Cape Prince of Wales in the Chukchi Sea (Figure 1). The offshore area around Sledge Island, several kilometers west of Nome, may contain significant amounts of gold in the sediment. Also, east of Nome about 76 km (41 miles) near Bluff, cliffs once mined for gold and silver may be sources for placers concentrated offshore. Offshore of Southeast Cape on St. Lawrence Island may also be worth exploring for gold as well as other heavy metals (e.g., copper, lead, zinc, molybdenum, and silver).

Other areas in Alaska, where onshore lode deposits of gold are near enough to the continental shelf to merit serious offshore exploration include the following: Captains Bay located within the western part of Alaska; the Aleutian Islands; west of Kodiak Island and around Unga and Popof Islands; lower Cook Inlet in Kamishak Bay extending around the lower end of Kenai Peninsula; and possibly Resurrection Bay near Seward Peninsula.

Beaches along the northern part of the Gulf of Alaska have been mined for nearly a century. Offshore exploration, however, has not proceeded with any real interest. Weather and lack of supporting facilities have been limiting factors to exploration. A reconnaissance study by Reimnitz and Plafker (1976) revealed concentrations of gold in the beach sediments of the Copper River Delta. The shelf area of the Gulf of Alaska, bordered by beaches containing placers, may have economic potential. Trace amounts of gold are commonly found in lag deposits that unconformably overlie marine clastic rocks characterized by glacial detritus (Yakataga Formation). The Yakataga Formation underlies much of the shelf and is the most likely source of placer gold found on the beach at Middleton Island. This implies some onshore transport of placer gold in this region.

The area offshore of Juneau appears to possess a reasonably good potential for gold placers (Tagg, 1979). Local conditions of intense glaciation, large lode gold occurrences, and extensive drainage onto the continental shelf contribute to a favorable setting. There are, however, other factors which discourage exploration such as very little sampling information available and possible wide area dispersion of any heavy metals.

Alaska continues to attract an active interest in onshore mining of gold while, with the exception of Norton Sound, offshore interest remains essentially inactive. Opportunities exist for the discovery of economically producible placer deposits in offshore regions where nearby (or onshore) sediment provinces include significant lode gold occurrences.

Gold and Platinum - Atlantic and Gulf of Mexico Shelves:

There are no known occurrences of gold or platinum placers on the continental shelves of the Atlantic and Gulf of Mexico Regions.

Gold and Platinum - Pacific Region:

Occurrences of gold flakes and platinum, in association with other mineral sands (e.g., black sands), have been found along the Washington coast from Cape Flattery to the Columbia River (Phillips, 1979).

Placer deposits of gold and platinum are likely to occur, in association with other heavy mineral deposits, offshore of present rivers and estuary systems (e.g., Columbia River). Different sediment types on the Washington shelf occur in bands parallel to the coast with nearshore sands and relict sands being the most likely repository for placers. The nearshore sands extend out to an approximate water depth of 90 m (295 ft) (Gross, and others, 1967) while relict sands are less continuous and are found at depths greater than 120 m (394 ft) on the outer shelf. Low stands of sea-level (Gross, and others, 1967) or lag deposits produced by breaking internal waves (Phillips, 1979) are interpretations given for the concentration of heavy minerals. Additional work is required to determine the economic potential of gold and platinum deposits offshore on the Washington shelf.

The coast of Oregon has experienced limited mining activity for gold and platinum placers since the turn of the century. Beaches and elevated terraces from Coos Bay south to the California border have received attention. Platinum group minerals have been located in beach sediments from the mouth of the Columbia River south to Crescent City, California. Offshore placer deposits, although not delineated at present, may exist within a nearshore sand facies that parallels the Oregon shoreline and extends to depths of over 100 m (62 mi). Favorable locations on the shelf may also include the southern coast, the area at the mouth of the Columbia River (Phillips, 1979), or other river systems where drainage patterns migrate through known gold or platinum bearing rocks.

Mining for gold along the northern California coast was initiated in the mid-1800's. Beaches and elevated terraces were preferred sites of mining activity. Gold has been identified in offshore sediments near Crescent City, California, and in southern California occurring off river mouths (Phillips, 1979). The offshore gold accumulations may be lag deposits resulting from erosion of Cenozoic deposits during postglacial rise in sea level.

Platinum has also been reported to occur in beach sediments near Crescent City as well as further south to Orick (Phillips, 1979). The Monterey Bay area has also been identified as a site for some platinum. Geomorphologically guided offshore reconnaissance sampling of sediments needs to be conducted to evaluate the potential for discovering gold and platinum placers on the California shelf.

Tin - Alaska Region:

Tin, in association with gold placers and other heavy minerals, has been reported to occur within a shoal which extends NNE from Cape Prince of Wales along the northwest portion of Seward Peninsula (Tagg, 1979). Since western Seward Peninsula is a significant resource area for tin, the offshore area appears to possess a favorable potential for tin placers.

Tin - Pacific/Gulf of Mexico/Atlantic Regions:

Occurrence of tin as placer deposits on the continental shelf is relatively unknown in the Pacific, Gulf of Mexico, and Atlantic offshore regions. Further sediment sampling is necessary in these offshore regions to determine potential for tin placers.

Heavy Minerals - Alaska Region:

Even though gold is of prominent interest, in terms of offshore mining, genuine interest in an array of heavy minerals (e.g., lead, silver, tin, and tungsten) has persisted, particularly in promising localities. Approximately 50 km (27 miles) east of Cape Prince of Wales heavy mineral placers have been reported and some production of lead, silver, tin, and tungsten has taken place (Tagg, 1979). Attention should also be directed toward the offshore area off the western end of St. Lawrence Island.

It is reasonable to conclude that offshore areas in Alaska that possess a fairly high potential for harboring gold placers may also include heavy minerals. For example, offshore Nome and Daniels Creek at Bluff; offshore of the western part of St. Lawrence Island, near Unga and Popof Islands west of Kodiak Island, Kamishak Bay, Shelikof Straits and most of southeast Alaska contain lead, silver, copper, platinum, antimony, and zinc, usually associated with gold (Tagg, 1979). The likelihood of finding heavy-mineral placers with lag deposits offshore of the Copper River Delta is also good (Reimnitz and Plafker, 1976). Intense glaciation in concert with widespread metalliferous outcrops and proximity of the Gulf of Alaska enhance the potential for discovering offshore heavy-mineral placers, given appropriate concentration mechanisms.

Heavy Minerals - Pacific Region:

A full suite of heavy minerals occur along the coast of Washington in a discontinuous manner. They are found as detrital placers within beach and estuarine sediments and include: platinum group, apatite, xenotime, zircon, sphene, rutile, leucosene, monazite, ilmenite and chromite (Phillips, 1979). As noted earlier, the Washington shelf sediments are differentiated into major types; nearshore sand, outer shelf silt-mud, and relict sands. This differentiation reflects on physical as well as biological processes operative in the area. Low-stands of sea level, winnowing effect, and bioturbation have, collectively and at different times, been responsible for distributing and concentrating heavy minerals on the shelf.

Favorable locations for heavy mineral placers occur in submerged beaches on the Washington shelf in the area south of the Hoh River at depths of 18 and 51 m (59 and 167 ft); off Grays Harbor at depths of 18, 26 to 33, and 44 to 51 m (59, 85 to 108, and 144 to 167 ft) (Venkanatham, 1970); and seaward of Willapa Bay spit at depths of 20 to 30 m (66 to 98 feet). The largest concentration of heavy minerals on the Washington and Oregon shelf occur seaward of the mouth of the Columbia River (Phillips, 1979). Byrne and Panshin (1966) reported greater than 30 percent heavy-mineral concentrations in sediments on the south side of the mouth of the Columbia River. These concentrations extend out to depths of 100 m (328 ft). Opaque minerals range between 6 percent and 15 percent concentration. Dredge spoils from the Columbia River may account for high concentration levels to the south (Figure 2).

Available information suggests reworking and concentration of older deposits containing heavy minerals by physical processes and bioturbation. Heavy minerals at shallow depths (< 40 m) may be acted upon and concentrated primarily by physical processes (Phillips, 1979).

The suite of heavy minerals found along the Oregon coast is similar to that found along Washington State, namely platinum group, apatite, zircon, sphene, rutile, monazite, and others. Generally, offshore deposits tend to occur seaward or adjacent to river systems. To the north, heavy minerals occur seaward of the Nehalem River and extend to depths of 65 m (213 ft).

Heavy mineral placers have also been reported off the Siltcoas River in depths of 55-65 m and the Umpqua River at 130-185 m (426-697 ft) in depth. As mentioned earlier, heavy-mineral placers with occurrences of gold have been uncovered seaward of Cape Blanco. Further out on the shelf, heavy minerals of high concentration (43 percent) are located near the shelf break adjacent to the Roque Submarine Canyon. Concentration of placers off the mouth of the Roque River at 80-90 m (262-295 ft) also show potential for recovery. In most cases, occurrences of heavy-mineral placers coincide with low stands of sea level.

Heavy-mineral placers along the California coast appear to be more limited than along Washington and Oregon. This is probably a function of a lack of research in the regions. With the exception of offshore Crescent City, only minor occurrences of heavy-mineral placers have been reported. Zircon and chromite concentrations may have economic value, although heavy mineral data is available only for part of the northern California shelf. Heavy-mineral occurrence appears to be similar (platinum group, apatite, zircon, shene, rutile, monazite and others) to the Washington and Oregon Shelf with the addition of barite, glauconite, and phosphorite. The California Shelf is fairly narrow and is incised by many submarine canyons. Detrital material may not remain for any duration on this part of the shelf because the canyons act as conduits for the transport of sediment to oceanic depths.

Heavy Minerals - Gulf of Mexico Region

Kyanite and sillimanite, along with garnet, rutile, zircon, monazite and ilmenite, are most common on the beaches and nearshore sediments around the mouth of the Apalachicola River on the gulf coast of Alabama and Florida (Nossaman, and others, 1968). In the western part of the Gulf minerals of the amphibole-pyroxene group are dominant. Mississippi River derived sediments, recent beach sands, and older reworked sediments off Louisiana contain heavy minerals; ilmenite and zircon are common. Interest has focused primarily on mining of calcium carbonate, in the form of coarse shell material, for cement manufacturing.

Heavy Minerals - Atlantic Region

As discussed earlier, the continental shelf along the eastern United States varies topographically and texturally along its extent. The shelf has been repeatedly emerged and submerged over the recent past as a consequence of glaciation. The shelf topography along the mid-Atlantic states is much smoother than the glaciated shelf bottom to the north, however, ridges and swales are common across this part of the shelf.

Heavy-mineral placers are and have been mined onshore from ancient beach sands along the coasts of New Jersey, Georgia, and Florida. An example includes Trail Ridge near Jacksonville, Florida (Manheim, 1979). Coastal plain deposits in New Jersey have also been a source of placer minerals, particularly ilmenite and zircon.

On the basis of existing information, it is difficult to evaluate the potential for offshore placers along the Atlantic shelf. Offshore sands have typically shown only about 1-4 percent total heavy-mineral concentration. However, the vast extent of these sands and abundance of titanium rich phases from loose sands suggest a fairly large resource of titanium (i.e., rutile, and ilmenite) and other minerals. Other heavy minerals in the suite include monazite, xenotime, amphibole group minerals, zircon, garnet, kyanite, sillimanite, staurolite and others. Sediments on the New England shelf are glacially derived and therefore the suite is apt to be immature (i.e., amphibole group and garnet abundant), whereas the shelf area to the south has more mature heavy-mineral suites (i.e., very little amphiboles and garnet) (Grosz, personal communication).

In a recently completed study of 71 grab samples from marine sediment deposits in Virginia, South Carolina, and northeastern Florida (A, B, and C, Figure 3). Comparisons of offshore heavy-mineral concentrations were made with results from previous onshore studies and onshore mining operations (Table 1). Offshore Virginia suites show larger concentrations of heavy minerals than offshore areas to the south and only slightly less than the richest onshore control area in South Carolina. In addition, though significant concentrations of heavy minerals occur offshore of Virginia, no economic deposits are found onshore (Grosz and Escowitz, 1983). Estimates of economic potential are not known owing to the lack of vertical control for the offshore area.

From the examination of 92 grab samples, Drucker (1983) identified 6 zones of heavy-mineral concentration within the inner New York Bight area as having economic potential. It was estimated that zircon accounted for the bulk of heavy minerals in zones 1, 2, and 3, and ilmenite was concentrated in zones 1, 4, and 6.

RESOURCE ESTIMATES

Alaska Region:

Alaska has produced approximately 30 million ounces of gold (Nossaman, and others, 1968) largely from deposits in or near the coastal regions. Placer deposits account for a majority of this total production. The region around Nome yielded about 5 million ounces, mainly from ancient and modern beaches.

The continental shelves of the Bering and Chukchi Seas possess, in part, a background concentration of gold in the order of 0.02-0.08 ppm mainly in particles 10-20 microns in size. Gold particles of a coarser size may exist on the inner parts of the shelves. The magnitude of these gold sources may be in the range of millions of ounces. The Gulf of Alaska may have the same potential for gold placers as the Bering and Chukchi Seas, possibly amounting to tens of millions of ounces in undiscovered resources.

Past production of platinum from placers on the Salmon River, Seward Peninsula and at Lituya Bay in southeastern Alaska has been estimated to be well over a half million ounces. Potential offshore resources of platinum may be in the order of tens or hundreds of thousands of ounces (Nossaman and others, 1968).

Heavy-mineral placers with high concentrations of magnetite and ilmenite may exist off southeastern Alaska near Kukwan where an alluvial deposit of several hundred million tons may have a magnetite content of 10 percent (Berg, Eberlein, and MacKerrett, 1964). It is conceivable that offshore magnetite and ilmenite placers may exceed millions of tons in these southeastern regions. Approximately 2,000 tons of placer tin has been mined on the western part of Seward Peninsula. The offshore potential for placer tin ranges from thousands to tens of thousands of tons (Nossaman, and others, 1968).

Atlantic and Gulf of Mexico Regions:

Because there are no known or postulated occurrences of offshore gold, platinum, or tin on the Atlantic and Gulf of Mexico continental shelves, it is not possible to estimate any placer extent or value at this time. Other heavy mineral placers have been located on the Atlantic and Gulf shelves and are discussed in terms of potential availability. Estimates show that the resource potential for titanium on the Atlantic shelf south of Long Island is over 1 million tons. Resource potential for heavy minerals on the Atlantic and Gulf of Mexico shelves is shown on Table 2. Mineral species found offshore Virginia in sand-size sediments include garnet, rutile, zircon, apatite, monazite, staurolite, glaucophane, and amphibole.

Pacific Region:

Placer gold concentrations along the Washington shelf range from 0.001 to 0.004 ounces per ton of sediment. These estimates are based on only a few samples containing gold (11 out of 52) collected by the Bureau of Mines in 1965 (Phillips, 1979). Platinum placers are unknown.

Five significant heavy-mineral concentrations on the Washington shelf, which includes three northern areas and two areas near the mouth of the Columbia River, cover an area of 540 km² (206 square miles). The total opaque mineral content for these areas, calculated to 1 m depth, is nearly 200,000 tons (Phillips, 1979). Black-sand placers are found in ancient and modern beaches in both northern and southern Oregon. Gold is present, however, only in small amounts (0.1-0.5 ppm) and is too fine grained to be recovered economically.

An opaque mineral concentration of 43 percent occurs in a sand facies at the shelf break adjacent to the Rogue Submarine Canyon. Heavy mineral concentrations on the Oregon shelf, which approximate about 10 percent of the sediment, cover an area of 1,530 km² (587 square miles). Chromite sand deposits containing about 30 million tons of concentrates (37-39 percent chrome) have been estimated for the Oregon shelf (Manheim and Hess, 1981). Estimates of heavy-mineral content on the Oregon shelf by Nossaman, and others, (1968) show a potential of several millions of tons each for ilmenite, rutile, and zircon.

On the northern California continental shelf, heavy mineral concentrations greater than 10 percent may cover an area of 20 km (8 square miles) (Phillips, 1979). Up to a million tons of heavy minerals may also be present on this part of the shelf. Chromite and zircon placers may be found on the shelf adjacent to Crescent City, California, but there is very little information available to evaluate resource potential. In those cases where placer deposits are judged to be submarginal if mined for these minerals alone, coproduct recovery may be possible, particularly in California and Oregon where co-occurrences of gold, platinum, ilmenite, and rutile might make offshore mining profitable. It is also conceivable that offshore southern Oregon-northern California concentrations of gold may exist in the order of hundreds of thousands of ounces, ilmenite and rutile in the range of millions of tons, and several hundreds of thousands of tons of zircon (Nossaman, and others, 1968).

Conclusion

The state-of-the-art technology for exploration and development of placers appears adequate. New and improved exploration techniques for mapping the sea floor, detection of metal placers, and navigation are currently being tested and preliminary results appear encouraging.

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Figure 2 Northern California and Oregon Coast

Figure 1 Bering Sea

Figure 3 Study areas in Virginia, South Carolina, and northeastern Florida (after Grosz, 1983).

Table 1 Comparison of the range and mean of heavy-mineral percentages of onshore with offshore samples.

	State	Number of Samples	Percent of SG >2.85			Mean ECON ¹
			Low	Mean	High	
ONSHORE	Virginia	80	0.01	0.65	11.40	30
	South Carolina	58	0.20	3.32	26.60	47
	Florida	80	0.02	0.75	10.01	68
OFFSHORE	Virginia	44	0.02	3.12	11.16	34
	South Carolina	10	0.08	1.13	4.60	29
	Florida	17	0.13	0.94	2.40	30

¹ ECON is defined as the sum of percent, in SG >2.85, concentration of ilmenite, leucoxene, rutile, zircon, sillimanite, and monazite.

Table 2 Potential resources of heavy minerals on the Atlantic and Gulf shelves (between state limits and the 200 meter contour; millions of short tons).

	Past production and known reserves from related sediments on land		Undiscovered marginal resources		Undiscovered sub-marginal resources	
	Atlantic	Gulf	Atlantic	Gulf	Atlantic	Gulf
Monazite	0.9	No data	0.1	3.7	1	not estimated
Ilmenite	54	"	109	90	1000	"
Rutile	1.9	"	1.4	12	14	"
Zircon	10	"	13.6	14	140	"
Kyanite and sillimanite	4	"	4	35	40	"
Staurolite	7	"	13.6	15	140	"
Garnet	No data	"	No data	3	No data	"